

The 4th World Technology Revolution;

The 1st letter of life in the new age

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Abstract

Nano names are heard a lot these days: nano science and technology, nano scientists, nano seminar, nano workshop, nano book and.... Why has this very small "nano" become so important and so popular? There are many reasons for the importance of nanoscience and nanotechnology. As we have seen so far, the properties of materials, such as their energy at the nanoscale, change relative to their large-scale state. Particle shrinkage, on the other hand, is a physical change, and it is not expected that the physical properties of matter will change with this physical change. This has led to the nanoscale being considered more than any other scale. Properties such as electrical conductivity, color, mechanical strength and even weight can vary at the nanoscale. For example, the conductivity of metals is well known. However, metals can be semiconductor or even insulated at the nanoscale! Hello to the fourth technology world revolution!

Keywords: Nanotechnology, importance of nanotechnology